

Outreach

Accessible
Interoperable
Reusable

Schools

Masterclass for pupils is further developed and executed in cooperation with Netzwerk Teilchenwelt.

Foto: Sandra Göttisheim
Credit: KIT

Science Slam

*Research Data
Management in
Middle-earth*

MS Wissenschaft

Decision tree exhibit for the exhibition in 2023. Material available under faszination.uni-bonn.de.

Lego model

A Lego model of the ALMA Observatory illustrates the operation of a radio interferometer.

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www.punch4nfdi.de

Fact sheet

- Netzwerk Teilchenwelt: <https://www.teilchenwelt.de/>
- Teaching material stands in connection with teacher training (Lehrkräftefortbildung) such as this event: <https://indico.hiskp.uni-bonn.de/event/714/>
- Report on the MS Wissenschaft exhibit: https://www.uni-bonn.de/en/news/university-of-bonn-exhibit-aboard-201cms-wissenschaft201d?set_language=en
- More information on the Lego ALMA model: <https://www.astro.uni-bonn.de/en/public/lego-alma-en>
- Award-winning Escape Room Idea "2051: Energy in Outer Space" <https://www.uni-bonn.de/en/news/university-of-bonn-wins-with-escape-room-about-energy-in-outer-space>
- Physics Show Musical PLANETAMOS <https://www.physik-astro.uni-bonn.de/physikshow/de/anmeldung>
- Regular Science Pub Format Astronomy on Tap Bonn <https://www.instagram.com/aotbonn/>

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